

**Quantitative Modeling of AI Data Center Emissions Under
Alternative Energy Policies**

Finn Case

Professor Startz

University of California Santa Barbara

Introduction

Artificial intelligence may be considered the greatest invention of the twenty-first century, and its influence is only growing. With models becoming more advanced and being implemented in almost every workplace environment, its computing power comes at a large environmental cost that is often overlooked. The rapid expansion requires large draws of energy, with data centers that house these models already using 4.4% of electricity in the United States in 2023, and forecasted to triple by 2028 if nothing is done (MIT Technology Review 2025, IEA 2024). In certain states such as Virginia, data centers already take up a quarter of all local energy demand (MIT Technology Review 2025). The rapid expansion of AI use is the fastest growing source of demand for energy in the country's economy, raising new concerns for clean energy, grid expansion and climate policy.

There are many clear externalities of AI growth. AI firms benefit from expanding their models at a large unchecked environmental cost, electrical grid strain and raising prices for nearby individuals. These negative externalities have the potential to change, yet have little incentive to do so, providing a strong argument for economic policy intervention (IMF 2025).

This paper will address the research question: *How can economic policy be used to reduce the environmental impact of AI usage in the United States?* Using current research reports this paper will cover the scale of the problem, estimations for power consumption, possible ways to reduce it, and finally decide which approach achieves an impactful result. The sources cover different perspectives and aspects of the question,

with some covering strictly data gathering, making economic policy suggestions, or giving different points of view into the problem.

The goal of the research is to find a balance between positive environmental change, and keeping AI innovation strong. It will be shown that policies like subsidies and taxes have a large impact on clean energy use, but a large cost to firms that would incentivise innovation. Options like a clean energy mandate combined with dynamic energy pricing lower environmental externalities while still keeping AI growth steady.

The research paper has 6 sections. Firstly, the framework will be established using outsourced data to set a baseline so the changes from each policy can be calculated, evaluated and compared. This will be followed with an explanation of each policy, including what it is, the strengths, weaknesses and calculating its estimated change from the baseline. The third section will then analyze the cost to firms as used for comparison later. Section 4 will briefly go over the survey results conducted. Section 5 will compare each of these policies based on their effectiveness, cost, outcome and feasibility to show why using both a clean energy mandate and dynamic energy pricing is the best option. Section 6 will sum up the data using visuals, along with the math behind it.

In order to determine the effectiveness of each policy, this paper uses a quantitative framework to link energy usage and carbon intensity to total emissions. This will allow for a consistent comparison across each policy type to be used in comparison for costs and create a measurable baseline.

Framework

This paper will be using a simple framework to evaluate the environmental impact of AI resulting from the proposed economic policy interventions. This framework will consist of determining the emissions of a scenario by taking into account the amount of electricity used and how much carbon is given off.

This will be calculated using:

$$**E (emissions) = Y (electricity consumed) x C (carbon impact)**$$

In this framework, E will be representing the total emissions from AI data centers. Y will represent the electricity consumed from the data center due to AI related work loads. C will represent the grams of CO₂ per kilowatt-hour. The reasoning for using these two variables is so that we can measure and compare how much electricity will be consumed by AI data centers in each scenario, along with how much carbon it will give off based on the amount of clean energy used. An example of a change in Y (electricity consumed) could be the amount of electricity used from search queries changing due to a tax policy. An example of C (carbon impact) varying would be the difference of clean energy use in somewhere like California in the afternoon, consuming 70 grams of CO₂ per kilowatt hour using solar energy vs during midnight which could be as high as 300 grams of CO₂ per kilowatt hour (MIT Technology Review 2025).

Although there are other environmental factors to AI use such as water consumption for cooling, non CO₂ air pollution, grid reliability, E-waste and multiple other things that will not be factored into the frameworks equation, these are still considered. They will be factored in either by decreasing with CO₂ changes if they are correlated, or directly mentioned in the paper if the policy would change one of these aspects as a cost of offsetting CO₂. The reason for CO₂ being the main variable is

because it's the most researched externality in this sector, easiest to track, and has a strong positive correlation with many of the mentioned variables.

This framework allows for a simple yet clear plan for how different economic policies will affect the issue. Some suggested policies lower E (emissions) by bringing down the Y (electricity consumed) such as funding more energy efficient AI hardware or setting efficiency standards. Other policies lower C (carbon impact) such as a carbon tax or a renewable energy subsidy. This number from the framework can then be used to compare it to other externalities and cost per policy to determine what options are best.

This framework also works as a strong baseline. This is because if left unchecked, AI will result in both rising Y (electricity consumed) and C (carbon impact) due to increased need for power that regenerative energy can not keep up with. The international monetary fund estimates that if we keep to the current economic policies in place, global carbon emissions from electricity generation will have a 5.5 percent increase by 2030. The International Energy Agency also projects an increase, specifically from U.S. data centers, that their energy demand will triple from 4.4 percent of energy used to 12 percent by 2028 due to AI growth. The trends clearly show that if nothing is done, there will be a devastating environmental impact. By structuring my paper and analysis around a simple framework for calculating emissions, we can clearly determine the tradeoffs between different policies and the change in emissions they result in.

Using data gathered by the International Energy Agency, we can create a baseline scenario for the framework based on projections. With the anticipated 12

percent increase by 2028 from 2023's 4,000 TWh demand, we can assume data centers consume 448 TWh per year by 2028 (4×1.12). Data centers use energy sources that are 48% more carbon intensive than the average US energy source (MIT Tech Review 2024). With the US carbon output average being about 385 grams of CO₂ per kWh using a weighted mean of sources being 60% fossil, 20% nuclear and 20% renewables (EIA 2024), the carbon intensity for a data center would be about 570 grams (385×1.48) of CO₂ per kWh. Using the model, we can establish a baseline of $(448 \times 10^9 \text{ kWh (converting TWh to kWh)}) \times (570 \text{ gCO}_2 \text{ per kWh}) =$ about 255 million metric tons of CO₂ per year.

The baseline used throughout this paper will assume a 448 TWh of annual electricity use for AI related activities with an average carbon intensity of 570 grams of CO₂ per kWh, resulting in an output of 255 million tons of CO₂ per year.

Carbon Tax

Carbon tax is a very direct and widely studied economic policy used for reducing emissions. A carbon tax works by placing a cost on each ton of CO₂ emitted, causing firms that use fossil fuel energy to pay for their environmental cost and damage to society. This influences them to lean towards cleaner alternatives since the real cost of high CO₂ output energy sources becomes more expensive. For AI, this policy would affect the amount of electricity data centers use to both train and run their models. Due to the fact the majority of the U.S. power grid runs on natural gas and coal, a carbon tax would increase the cost of using these carbon intensive sources. This creates the needed incentive to bring down AI data centers' impact by shifting their sourcing towards renewable energy.

Using the prior mentioned framework ($E = Y \times C$), we can see that a carbon tax would primarily reduce C but also Y . Looking at evidence found in the sources, it shows that when implementing a \$30 per ton of carbon tax, energy levels decrease globally by about 10 percent in the energy sector, specifically from coal and natural gas (Resources for the future, 2022). Since this tax is priced based on carbon output, the biggest part of the energy industry that would be priced out would be coal due to it being the highest CO₂ per kWh energy source, causing a substantial switch from coal to natural gas and renewables (RFF). Using the 10% projection in the model, it would lower the 570 grams of CO₂ per kWh average to 513 due to the change coming from coal and oil sources. This 10 percent loss also affects the Y variable since it brings down the total amount of energy consumed by AI data centers, bringing 448 down to 403.

This would change the equation to $(403 \times 10^9 \text{ kWh}) \times (513 \text{ grams of CO}_2 \text{ per kWh}) = 206 \text{ million metric tons of CO}_2 \text{ per year}$. Although this is still large, it decreased CO₂ externality by over 55 million tons. This policy would also generate tax revenue, estimated to generate $(\$30 \times 206 \text{ million metric tons of CO}_2) = 6.18 \text{ billion a year}$.

Even though this decrease would be smaller than some of the later mentioned policies, Resources for the Future makes it clear that this carbon tax creates long term change in decarbonizing the power sector and increasing competitiveness of renewable energy relative to fossil fuels. The downside to this would be making it harder for some to enter the industry because of the requirement to pay for a more expensive power source. Along with this, if this carbon tax is not across all states, AI data centers would move to where there are less stringent laws and increase carbon production in certain grids, becoming even more unclean.

Although it has potential downsides, a carbon tax has a large positive environmental impact and incentivises AI data centers to align with environmental and public goals through low carbon AI processing.

Clean Energy Subsidy

A clean energy subsidy is a different approach that would aim at lowering emissions by reducing the cost of renewable energy when in comparison to the currently used fossil fuels. Unlike the tax that discourages CO₂ output, the clean energy subsidy would push firms to increase funding in clean energy, causing less negative impact to AI technology growth and more focus on building clean energy infrastructure. It would pay firms for sourcing or constructing low CO₂ impact energy sources such as solar, wind or nuclear that are switching from unclean sources like coal, biomass or natural gas, being paid per CO₂ ton saved from the swap. To begin this subsidy, it would be best used if it only began subsidizing those who switched from coal since it has the highest CO₂ output, and later pushing out biomass and natural gas. This would lead to the quickest impact because of coal's large environmental impact. In the AI sector, the subsidy would have the potential to lower the carbon impact of electricity used by its related data centers by encouraging AI companies to invest in renewable energy alternatives, since it's both cleaner and also cheaper under the subsidy than the fossil fuel based alternative. This could involve the AI companies constructing their own clean energy infrastructure or take part in long-term renewable power purchase agreements with electricity companies. Using the model $Y = E \times C$, a clean energy subsidy would primarily aim to impact C, the carbon impact, by pushing a faster and more full shift to low carbon output energy generation options.

By looking at the baseline scenario using the model, total electricity demand by 2028 is projected to be $Y = 480$ TWh (IEA) with the average carbon intensity of the current US data center grid being about 570 grams CO₂/kWh (IEA, MIT). Coal makes up 30 percent of energy production for AI centers (IEA), and gives off 820 grams of CO₂. If $\frac{2}{3}$ of coal was swapped for the average CO₂ output of clean energy sources (using weighting based on use), being 30 grams per kWh, it would decrease the CO₂ to average output of the datacenters to 412 grams of CO₂/kWh.

Using these assumptions in the equation, total annual emissions would decline from the baseline of 570 to 412 by implementing the clean energy subsidy. Plugging it into the equation, we get 198 million metric tons, a big change from the 255 million tons baseline (480×10^9 kWh (converting TWh to kWh)) \times (412 gCO₂ per kWh). Not only would this cause a direct decrease, but the subsidy would build out a cleaner grid through investments that could spill over into other industries and have an even greater effect outside the equation. It could lead to a more resilient grid due to more power supply and renewable technology innovations for the AI industry and beyond.

In order to prevent firms from exploiting the subsidy by creating coal energy infrastructure just so it can be switched to renewables for the monetary benefit, this policy would also have to include an eligibility requirement. The requirement would be that firms have to show their subsidised energy is a clear and large reduction from their past year average CO₂ output. This would make building coal infrastructure in order for it to be swapped for clean energy not worth the subsidy for firms who are trying to abuse the policy, yet would assist firms trying to add more clean energy as their supplier. This would also mean only clean energy that has a CO₂ output of under 50

grams per kWh (solar, wind etc) would get the subsidy to stop firms from swapping from coal to something slightly better, such as oil.

Yet the clean energy subsidy policy would have its own set of drawbacks. Subsidies require public funding which comes at the cost of tax payers, and if not properly implemented, AI companies could take advantage of the policy or be overcompensated in a scenario where they would already be spending their own funds on clean energy. This could lead to a poorly designed incentive that would cause large firms to get large subsidy payments, and lock out smaller ones from achieving them, lowering competition and market efficiency, while having the weight of the subsidy being borne by the taxpayer (ACEEE White Paper 2025). The cost of the subsidy would be the quantity saved multiplied by the subsidy, costing the taxpayer 2.25 billion dollars annually (273 million tons - 198 million tons = 75 million tons, 75 million tons * \$30 = 2.25 billion). But if structured correctly, a clean energy subsidy has the potential to lower the carbon per kWh used from data centers by supporting a grid run on clean energy that could benefit AI and outside industries for the future.

Dynamic Energy Pricing

Dynamic energy pricing is a different kind of policy than the previous two. The idea of this option is to get certain AI data centers to do the processing when there is more clean energy available. This would mean that an AI related task could be processed in California one part of the day when there is access to solar power to draw from, and then switch to a data center in Maine that is pulling from wind turbines at night. This would directly affect C (carbon intensity) in the model. Dynamic Energy pricing has the potential to be the most effective and efficient short term policies for

reducing environmental strain (ACEEE 2025). This policy could be implemented by mandating allocation of workloads across data centers to where clean energy is available. Although this would not force data centers to build in clean energy locations directly, naturally they would be built in places with access to clean energy so that the new ones would be able to do more work loads since firms have to direct work to the ones with low CO2 impact.

The reason for this policy works so well is because of the drastic difference in average marginal emission rates across the US based on when their peak hours are, varying by over 250 grams of CO2 per kWh (MIT, World Nuclear Association). This means that switching from a data center at peak hours to another where there is access to more clean energy can significantly reduce their carbon footprint. AI workloads are not affected by where the processing gets done, and this is currently already being done by AI companies to find where energy is cheapest, but with this dynamic energy pricing policy, firms would have to use the cleaner sourced energy option instead. With the United States getting 60 percent of its energy from fossil fuels (EIA), we could estimate for data centers this would shift between $\frac{1}{6}$ to $\frac{1}{2}$ of its fossil fuel energy (10% to 30% of total) to a blend of cleaner energy sources. This would result in the average use for data centers shifting from 570 down to about 426 grams of CO2/kWh $((0.5*579.9$ (*fossil fuel CO2 output*)) + $(0.2*12$ (*nuclear energy CO2 output, based on current use*) + $(0.3*48$ (*clean energy CO2 output, based on current use*)). Using the framework established, this policy would primarily lower C because of the constant shifting of a lower carbon output energy source. If we plug this change into the model (490 TWh x 426 grams of CO2/kWh) we could get about 208 million metric tons of CO2 output per

year, being a 18 percent reduction from the baseline of 255. This would be both a quick solution, and one with an extremely large impact.

Another key aspect of AI is training the model, which can consume large quantities of power. Training AI models accounts for about 40% of total AI related electricity used, and is something that needs to be directly addressed (Cornell, Patterson). Model training is something that is highly schedulable, and not needed to be done at certain times of day. Because of this, data centers could have the training done at times and regions that have more renewable energy available (peak hours are 4-9). This would be guided by dynamic energy pricing so that training would never be done during peak periods and reserved for when there is little load on the grid and access to the most clean energy. According to Patterson's analysis, mapping AI training related workloads to cleaner grids can lower emissions by a factor of 5-10x, and lowering emissions by 15-20% (in line with our current math). By not just allocating AI task workloads to cleaner grids, but also targeting AI model training, we can take advantage of being able to choose the cleanest times and locations for it to be processed.

Yet this policy has its own challenges. The first challenge would be transparency and tracking of emission rates for energy sources and AI data centers so that loads can be shifted properly. Second, we are assuming that data workloads can be shifted with limited energy efficiency losses or latency problems. Although this is a fairly safe assumption since it is already done for financial reasons, there may be a small environmental cost to moving workloads. Although these are potential threats to this policy, with correct rules for reporting and proper grid coordination, there is much potential.

Dynamic energy pricing still remains as a strong potential policy due to its cost effectiveness and potential for immediate implementation. Unlike the previously mentioned taxes and subsidies, it would not require large public spending or the same strain on the market, but simply involve mandates to guide AI use to cleaner energy sources. While being a short term fix, it will only become more effective as AI power consumption grows, while pushing the market for investment in the clean energy industry to grow to feed AI data centers.

Clean Energy Mandate

A clean energy mandate would require AI data centers to source a certain portion of their electricity use from low carbon impact energy providers. It would require the percentage to have a CO₂ output average of less than or equal to the stated mandate. This policy would directly target C (Carbon intensity) in the framework with the goal of lessening how many carbon heavy energy sources are used. This mandate would achieve this in two ways. Firstly, new AI data centers would be constructed in locations with access to a clean energy grid so that they can fit the rules of the mandate. This would allow for many current data centers to continue functioning as normal, lessening the short term impact of the mandate. It would also lead to the future construction of data centers to have access to cleaner energy, to reduce instances such as Virginia, where as prior mentioned, have a quarter of all local energy used on data centers while also being one of the most carbon intensive energy sourced states. The second way this mandate would work would be to incentivise future construction and investment into clean energy sources to power new AI data centers, as well as support current ones that are relying on carbon intensive energy sources. This paper proposes that this

mandate would require 50 percent of energy to come from clean energy sources, which would push for large change, while also still allowing for data centers to continue without too much impact and minimise slowing down AI advancements. With 50 percent more electricity being generated with fossil fuels in the US than 20 years ago (World Nuclear), this mandate is set on reversing that. The goal would be to increase the 50 percent as time goes on to make the change more impactful while keeping the AI space growing and competitive with other nations.

Currently, 60 percent of power comes from natural gas and coal and almost 40 percent comes from solar, wind or nuclear (IEA) . With the plan to push that 40 percent towards 50, we can calculate a drastic change in CO₂ output. Using the clean energy change of using the 3 clean energy sources, we get an average of 30 grams of CO₂/kWh (World Nuclear). This being swapped for 10 percent of the fossil fuel heavy alternative projection (726 weighted average) would create a change of 70 grams of CO₂ per kWh (Changing 10% from 726 to 30 of the 570 from the framework results in a new average of 500). Plugging this into the framework, we get an output of 240 million metric tons $((480 \times 10^9 \text{ kWh}) \times (500 \text{ gCO}_2 \text{ per kWh}))$. This represents a 6 percent reduction in total CO₂ emissions per year from AI data centers by lowering C (Carbon intensity) in the model.

This option does have its own problems. Although the percentage of clean energy would start low and increase over time, it would still require investment and would slow AI growth. It would raise costs for firms that could otherwise be investing in AI innovation. It would also hurt certain firms more than others, targeting those who currently have their computing done in carbon heavy states, reducing competition in the

space. To pay for the admin costs of monitoring this policy also slows AI technology innovation, where it is generally standard to recover costs through facility compliance fees which can be as high as \$70,000 (California Clean Energy Commission), yet most data centers spend twice that on power alone per day making this a trivial amount of money. Lastly it would require a lot of supervision to implement, needing a way to monitor where the data centers are sourcing their power from. Although it has its problems, a clean energy mandate would result in fast change, minimal government spending, and large investment in clean energy that could potentially affect other sectors as well.

Transparency and Reporting Requirement

An additional policy that would be needed to support the previously discussed plans is a nationwide requirement for transparency and reporting for AI related data centers. Currently, most AI data centers have no requirement and do not disclose their electricity consumption, sources of carbon intensity or water usage (MIT Technology Review, 2025). This makes it very difficult to regulate and evaluate their environmental impact as well as determine changes from policies. A requirement of transparency and reporting would mean that data centers must submit verified reports on their energy use, emissions, cooling systems and other environmental related externalities. This gives policy makers the information they need to monitor, implement and change the proposed interventions to make sure they are being followed as well as determine what is best for the situation. Although this policy would have no direct impact on emissions and make no change to the framework equation, it is needed for the other economic tools to work, and provides much more accurate data than what we have now. Having

this requirement be nationwide would also stop the possible problem of data centers moving to states that have less firm regulations and monitoring in order to avoid this policy. This requirement would ensure better data collection and strengthen all the mentioned policies resulting in accountability and environmental change for AI firms.

Cost to Firms

While the main goal of these policies is to lessen environmental impact, the cost to firms and AI development must be factored in. Something to be considered is that clean energy is cheaper per kWh (being about \$0.006 per kWh vs \$0.01 per kWh for unclean) yet it is not used currently because of the cost of constructing the infrastructure to provide it. That is why policies can be implemented to force firms to use it, in turn creating a market that would need to be filled. This would lead to electricity companies investing in clean energy to supply the demand. Much of these costs would be reflected on energy providers through the large cost of constructing clean energy sources, and limited to not being borne by the AI firms due to current laws in place preventing them from raising electricity costs. Although this could be altered to assist the energy firms by making energy cost the normal rate of \$0.0095 for data centers. This would keep AI firms paying the rate they were already supplied at, and also incentivise energy companies to enter this market further. For the firm cost comparison, we will assume that the price is kept at this \$0.0095 per kWh to both assume a worst scenario for the firm, and also the most reasonable scenario in order to help the electricity company find more reason to supply the demand for clean energy.

Survey Results

To add to my research, I conducted a short survey amongst UCSB students taking statistical economics (Econ 5) that checked their understanding and attitudes towards AI's environmental impact. I had 44 responses, almost half of which said they used AI tools daily, with over half saying they were aware of AI's large energy consumption. When asked if a small carbon related fee would impact their use, 54 percent said it would not affect either use. This suggests that certain price related policies may not be as effective. Of those surveyed, a large percentage supported policies that would offset emissions, which aligns well with the conclusion that energy mandates and dynamic pricing could be more effective than a tax or subsidy. Although it was a small survey amongst exclusively UCSB Economics 5 students possibly resulting in strong bias, it showed awareness about that issue, yet a low willingness to limit usage. This only reinforces the idea that we need policies that limit supply side energy usage and carbon output, and cannot let the market take its course.

Policy	CO2 Output in million metric	CO2 Change % from	Cost/Revenue For	Cost/Revenue For Firms
---------------	-------------------------------------	--------------------------	-------------------------	-------------------------------

	tons per year	baseline	Government	
Baseline Framework	273	-	-	-
Carbon Tax	206	-19%	+\$6.63 Billion	-\$7.66 billion
Clean Energy Subsidy	198	-22%	-\$2.25 Billion	-\$2.83 billion
Dynamic Energy Pricing	208	-18%	Administrative costs (\$70 million each year for first 5 years (NREL))	-\$4.65 billion
Clean Energy Mandate	240	-6%	Based on state, generally 0 due to state compliance fees covering cost	-\$2.24 billion

Conclusion

Each of the proposed policies uses a different technique to combat the environmental externalities of the growing AI industry, having different costs, effectiveness, feasibility, externalities and weaknesses.

Firstly, the carbon tax is a commonly discussed option, placing a price on emissions that incentivises a swap towards cleaner energy alternatives. The main strength of this option is creating a long term solution that also generates revenue. Yet the problem is it is not as effective as some of the other options, it would need country wide coordination across states or be a federal tax so that data centers do not just move to where the tax is lowest, and it creates market inefficiencies that slow down AI growth, with the entire cost being placed on firms.

A clean energy subsidy provides a monetary incentive for those switching from high carbon output energy sources to lower, cleaner ones. This is a strong option because it has a high impact and supports AI research and development. Yet this would require large public funding, costing tax payers billions, and could be overcompensating firms that would already be making these switches naturally. This policy would require careful and thoughtful implementation to be effective.

Dynamic energy pricing has the most immediate effect by shifting workloads to data centers that have access to clean energy in order to reduce emissions. Its strength is its quick results and low public monetary cost, using grid coordination and emission data to work effectively. It is also a technique that is being done by data centers, but currently just to push workloads to the cheaper option, not the cleaner one.

The clean energy mandate is a more structural option. This would require a set percentage of energy used by AI firms to come from clean energy sources, setting future expansion to pull almost exclusively from low CO₂ options. Although it has a low effectiveness, it is very low cost for the tax payer, could be implemented along with other policies, and causes little market inefficiency.

If we measure each policy by cost effectiveness, we can see who pays and how much per ton of CO₂ is reduced. A carbon tax would generate income for the government, but cost firms billions. A clean energy subsidy would cost the government or tax payer 30 dollars per ton. A dynamic pricing administration costs make it cost about 1.5 dollars per ton, being significantly lower. Finally the clean energy mandate would have a smaller cost, yet in turn smaller environmental change. Although looking at cost is only one externality of these policies, it is valuable information for making

decisions on which is a stronger option by comparing who is paying and how much each costs.

After comparing each policy, the most effective implementation would be using both a clean energy mandate with dynamic energy pricing, and monitoring it using mandatory transparency reporting. Using this combination, we can make sure that AI data centers are moving data workloads to places with clean energy, and forced to do so by the clean energy mandate, which makes sure there will be both a quick and long term definitive impact. This is all monitored and measured to see it is effectively being used by the mandatory transparency reports. This combination is also low cost in comparison to something like a subsidy, while also having near the same environmental change. By focusing on lowering emissions through energy sourcing, timing and transparency, the use of these policies together will create the greatest environmental impact for the cost, while minimising market inefficiency and disruptions to AI innovation and economic growth.

Table 1 summarizes each of the evaluated policies and displays estimated emission reductions, impact to firms, and impacts to the government/taxpayer.

In conclusion, economic policy has the potential to make a substantial reduction in AI's environmental impact by implementing supply side interventions. Using both the discussed dynamic energy pricing and clean energy mandate policies, supported by transparency and reporting requirements, we can balance environmental change with AI growth. They work together using dynamic pricing to immediately shift workloads where available, while the clean energy mandate ensures a long term solution for a cleaner grid. Transparency requirements allow both policies to function and be monitored

appropriately. These tools create a realistic future of sustainable AI development that is both supporting the private goals of AI development, while still achieving environmental progress.

Policy Comparison Assuming Government costs were equal

(These are all estimations that would most likely not hold, but for use in comparison. I will be making each total cost (government + firm cost) = to \$1 billion)

Carbon Tax total Cost = \$1 billion at current model

Change: 19%

Clean Energy Subsidy = decrease subsidy by 80.3% to 5.91, total cost would be \$1 billion ($0.197(-\$2.25 \text{ billion} - \$2.83 \text{ billion}) = \1 billion)

Change: -4.33% ($-22\% * 0.197$), yet decreased clean energy infrastructure.

Dynamic Energy Pricing = to decrease the cost from \$4.65 billion to \$1 billion, we decrease hours for the price change by 78.5% from 5 to 1.05 ($5 * 0.215$) which results in costs being \$1 billion ($0.215 * 4.66$).

Change: -3.87% ($-18\% * 0.215$)

Clean Energy Mandate = To change the proposed clean energy mandate of 50 percent, we can decrease it by 55.36 percent to result in a mandate of 22.32%, making cost equal at \$1 billion ($0.4464 * \2.24 billion).

Change: -2.24% ($-6\% * 0.4464$)

Cost for firms

Baseline - $(726 \text{ (unclean average)} - 570 \text{ (data center average)}) / ((726 \text{ (unclean average)} - \text{clean energy})) = 156/696 = 0.2241 = 22.4\%$ clean energy.

Clean energy weighted average cost per Wh = \$0.05 (EIA)

Carbon Tax - $(726 - 513)/696 = 213/696 = 0.3057 = 30.6\%$ Clean energy

$30.6\% - 22.4\% - (30.6 \times 0.1 \text{ (to account for change in Y)}) = 4.6\%$ change in clean energy used

$4.6\% \times 448 \text{ kWh} = 20.61 \text{ TWh} \rightarrow 20.61 \text{ TWh} \times 5 \text{ cents per kWh} = \1.03 billion

$\$1.03 \text{ billion} + 6.63 \text{ billion from tax} = \$7.66 \text{ billion cost to firms}$

Clean energy Subsidy - $(726 - 412)/696 = 314/696 = 0.4511 = 45.11\%$

$45.11\% - 22.4\% = 22.7\%$ change in clean energy used

$22.7\% \times 448 \text{ TWh} = 101.696 \text{ TWh} \rightarrow 101.696 \text{ TWh} \times 5 \text{ cents per kWh} = \5.08 billion

$\$5.08 \text{ billion} - \text{subsidy of } \$2.25 \text{ billion} = \$2.83 \text{ billion cost to firms}$

Dynamic Energy Pricing - during peak hours (4-9), renewable energy is more expensive at 50 cents per kWh vs 0.45 cents per kWh for fossil fuels due to demand.

$5/24 = 0.208$, $0.208 \text{ (percent of year being peak periods)} \times 448 \text{ TWh} = 93.33 \text{ MWh}$, $93 \text{ TWh} \times 5 \text{ cents more per kWh} = \4.65 billion

Clean energy mandate - $(726 - 500)/696 = 226/696 = 0.324 = 32.4\%$

$32.4\% - 22.4\% = 10\%$ change in clean energy used

$10\% \times 448 \text{ kWh} = 44.8 \text{ TWh} \rightarrow 44.8 \text{ TWh} \times 5 \text{ cents per kWh} = \$2.24 \text{ billion cost to firms}$

Percent Carbon Decrease with Cost held Constant (above)

Dollars Spent on Clean Energy Infrastructure in Billions (above)

Cost/Revenue to Government and Cost for Firms

Cost/Revenue to Government vs Firms in Billions (above)

PYTHON MODELING: <https://github.com/finnrcase/ai-data-center-policy-model>

Work Cited

IEA (2025), *Energy and AI*, IEA, Paris <https://www.iea.org/reports/energy-and-ai>,
Licence: CC BY 4.0

O'Donnell, James. "We Did the Math on AI's Energy Footprint. Here's the Story You Haven't Heard." *MIT Technology Review*, MIT Technology Review, 1 Aug. 2025, www.technologyreview.com/2025/05/20/1116327/ai-energy-usage-climate-footprint-big-tech/.

Mahmut Kandemir Mahmut Kandemir Professor. "Why AI Uses so Much Energy-and What We Can Do about It." *Institute of Energy and the Environment*, 8 Apr. 2025, iee.psu.edu/news/blog/why-ai-uses-so-much-energy-and-what-we-can-do-about-it.

Nvidia. "Nvidia Sustainability Report Fiscal Year 2024." *Nvidia Report*, images.nvidia.com/aem-dam/Solutions/documents/FY2024-NVIDIA-Corporate-Sustainability-Report.pdf. Accessed 6 Sept. 2025.

Bogmans, Christian, et al. "Power Hungry: How Ai Will Drive Energy Demand." *IMF*, 22 Apr. 2025, www.imf.org/en/Publications/WP/Issues/2025/04/21/Power-Hungry-How-AI-Will-Drive-Energy-Demand-566304.

Esrām, Nora, and Camron Assadi. 2025. "Future-Proof AI Data Centers, Grid Reliability, and Affordable Energy: Recommendations for States." *American Council for an Energy-Efficient Economy (ACEEE)*, April 7, 2025

Aldy, Joseph E., et al. "Considering a Carbon Tax: Frequently Asked Questions." *Issue Brief, Resources for the Future*, 1 Nov. 2012, <https://www.rff.org/publications/issue-briefs/considering-a-carbon-tax-frequently-asked-questions/>.

World Nuclear Association. "Carbon Dioxide Emissions From Electricity." *World Nuclear Association*, 3 Sept. 2024, <https://world-nuclear.org/information-library/energy-and-the-environment/carbon-dioxide-emissions-from-electricity>.

Inspire Clean Energy. "Cost of Renewable Energy: Does Clean Energy Cost More?"

Inspire Clean Energy, [InspireCleanEnergy.com](https://www.inspirecleanenergy.com), 2025,

<https://www.inspirecleanenergy.com/blog/clean-energy-101/cost-of-renewable-energy>.

Patterson, David, et al. "The Carbon Footprint of Machine Learning Training Will

Plateau, Then Shrink." arXiv preprint arXiv:2204.05149, 11 Apr. 2022,

<https://arxiv.org/abs/2204.05149>.

NRG Clean Power. "Navigating 2024 SCE Time-Of-Use Rates." NRG Clean Power, 23

Sept. 2024,

[https://nrgcleanpower.com/learning-center/sce-time-of-use-rates/#:~:text=Table_title:%20Understanding%20Rate%20Structures%20Table_content:%20header:%20%7C,\(9%20PM%20%E2%80%93%208%20AM\):%20\\$0.20/kWh%20%7C](https://nrgcleanpower.com/learning-center/sce-time-of-use-rates/#:~:text=Table_title:%20Understanding%20Rate%20Structures%20Table_content:%20header:%20%7C,(9%20PM%20%E2%80%93%208%20AM):%20$0.20/kWh%20%7C).